

The Proverbs and Tirukkural as Eternal Pieces of Memorable Literature

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K. Saranyadeeipka

Assistant Professor, Department of English

Gonzaga College of Arts And Science for Women, Krishnagiri

Abstract

This article lays center of attention on the intelligence which is the subject matter under the value system of life discussed in The Proverbs and The Tirukkural. It also throws radiance on how these enhance and enable the readers of literature to go ahead a life of morality. Both the works are the quintessence of great wisdom which had crystallized in the social consciousness of the human society. The Proverbs and Tirukkural as Eternal Pieces of Memorable Literature

The Book of Proverbs consists of nearly 3000 Proverbs, most of them by king Solomon; it also has an appendix of sayings of other wise men such as Agur and Lemuel. Tirukkural is a monumental work written in Tamil by Tiruvalluvar. It consists of 1330 terse, couplets. Dom Bernard Orchard makes an observation on the former work: Proverbs in The Bible is a human work written by men according to the current mode of literary expression and intended to be understood according to the rules of contemporary human language .

The Book of Proverbs belongs to the Wisdom Literature of Israel. Certain other texts in The Bible too may come under the same label in respect of their genre: To this literary genre also belong Job, Ecclesiastes, some of the Psalms in the Old Testament, Ecclesiasticus and the Wisdom of Solomon in the Apocrypha which form a great 27 body of Wisdom Literature which existed throughout the Near East in the ancient times (The Interpreter’s Bible Vol.IV 767).

It is an accepted fact that Comparative Literature is an academic discipline and a subject of scholarly investigation. It is essentially a humanistic education aiming at evaluating a work of art with other areas of knowledge and art. As David Malone puts it, “the fullest meaning and the final evaluation of a piece of literature can result only from comparison”. (P2) Human life is actually a major theme which includes not only social and political issues but also the probing, searchings and speculations of philosophy, truths and revelations of religion and morality in its fullest measure. A moral sense is traditionally considered a unique attribute of the human personality. The transformation from a solely biological organism to a socially responsible individual is the hallmark of the development of personality and a shared social development is necessary for viable human life.

Moral norms are usually interpreted as values of life, regarded high among the most attractive guides to conduct. Philosophers who profess moral values display wide agreement on the fundamental rules of morality. These include rules prohibiting persons from killing other persons, from inflicting injury on them or from depriving them of freedom and opportunity.

The Proverbs and The Tirukkural present some of the most essential codes of conduct to human beings. The core of the message presented by these two classics is 'morality'. Though both classics are separated widely by time and space, they justify truly the observation, "Great minds think alike".

The Proverbs is nothing but a collection of topical maxims and a product of the Wisdom school in Isreal. Solomon's proverbs were written by 931 B.C and under Solomen, Israel were at its spiritual. According to I kings 4.32, he spoke 3,000 proverbs. Only about 800 of his 3000 proverbs are included in the two solomonic collections in the book of Proverbs. No man was better qualified than soloman to be the principal contributor. He asked for wisdom and God granted it to him to such a degree that people from foreign lands came to hear him speak. His breadth of knowledge, aptitude, skill and perception were found to extraordinary. It is likely that Solomon collected and edited proverbs other than his own. According to the Ecclesiastes, "he pondered and sought out and set in order many proverbs. (P 666)

The Proverbs is one of the few Biblical books that clearly spell out their purpose.

"That man may know wisdom and instruction, understand words of insight, receive instruction in wise dealing, righteousness, justice and equity; that prudence may be given to the simple, knowledge and discretion to the youth – the- wise man also may hear and increase in learning and the man of understanding acquire skill, to understand a proverb and a figure, the words of the wise and their riddles" (The Interpreter's Bible 97)

'Kural' means anything short. It is a couplet containing a simple complete idea, often expressed in an epigrammatic form. It is a form that is admirably suited to the expression of ideas and Tiruvalluvar has handled this difficult medium with extraordinary skill and felicity. The combination of brevity of expression, grace of language, metre and highly refined ethical ideas make Tirukkural a unique literary work. Tirukkural contains 1330 couplets. There are one hundred and thirty-three chapters, each chapter containing ten couplets. Each is headed by one major idea such as 'friendship', 'wisdom', 'justice' and so on. The ten verses under each major idea enable the poet to expound one particular idea and various aspects of that idea in depth under different circumstances and conditions. Tirukkural is considered to be antecedent of Cilappatikaram and Manimekalai because the latter classics quote from Tirukkural. Obvious language resemblance could be seen between Tirukkural and Cankam works quite often. In Tirukkural, the style of structuring the couplets and the mode of expression of ideas belong to one person. The following quotation speaks better for the authorship of the ancient Tamil classic. It says:

"There is considerable internal evidence to show that the whole text belongs to one another. Apart from the prosodic metre which is throughout the same, the general pattern to which the text is made to conform and certain mannerisms of expression go to show that the text is from the pen of one and the same author" (P xiii)

Wisdom is the subject under ethics of life discussed in the Proverbs and Tirukkural. Wise knowledge about facts leads a man in the right path just as ignorance leads him to face undesirable consequences. Human mind is freed only when sparkling revelations about truth occur. This type of revelation occurs when one goes on reading scriptures, didactic document and maxims as found in the Proverbs and Tirukkural.

References

1. Eliade, Mercea. The Encyclopedia of Religion vol –II New York : Macmillan Publishing Company, 1987.
2. “Ecclesiastes 12” The open Bible New York: Thomas Nelson Publishing Company, 1985.
3. Proverbs: 2 to 6 from The Interpreter’s Bible vol –iv New York : Abington Press, 1939.
4. N. Subramanian and R. Rajalakshmi The Concordance of Tirukkural Madurai: Enness Publications, 1984.
5. Thiruvalluvar. Thirukkural. Ed. Dr. M.Varadharajan, Madras: Thirunelveli South India Saiva Sidhdhanta Kazhagam Ltd., Chennai. 1977.
6. Kasturi Sreenivasan. Tirukkural Translation. Coimbatore: Kasturi Sreenivasan Trust. 1983.